

UNVEILING THE DIGITAL UNDERWORLD: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF ILLICIT DRUG ACTIVITIES IN TELEGRAM GROUPS

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Abstract : The contemporary digital landscape, characterized by the ubiquitous presence of social media platforms, has witnessed a concerning trend: the proliferation of illicit drug trade and consumption facilitated by online chat groups. This research endeavour to conduct a systematic examination of this phenomenon within a sample size of 150 public chat groups on the Telegram platform. Employing rigorous methodologies, including a thorough analysis of chat histories, this study seeks to elucidate the intricate dynamics that underpin the promotion of illicit drug peddling and usage among group members. By discerning patterns of interaction and discourse, the research aims to delineate the mechanisms through which these virtual spaces serve as conduits for the exchange of illegal substances and the normalization of their consumption. Moreover, the study endeavour to highlight the broader societal implications of such activities, emphasizing the potential for long-term harm and the erosion of public health and safety. In light of these findings, the research advocates for the implementation of robust forensic examination techniques, particularly within the domain of cyber forensics, to effectively combat the proliferation of illicit drug trade and usage in online environments. Furthermore, it underscores the necessity for updated regulatory frameworks, such as the NDPS act of 1985 and IT Rules of 2021, to address the evolving challenges posed by illicit activities in digital domains and safeguard the well-being of individuals and communities. By offering actionable insights grounded in empirical evidence, this research aims to inform policy development, law enforcement strategies, and platform governance practices aimed at mitigating the deleterious impact of illicit drug trade and usage within virtual communities.

Index Terms - Illicit Drug Peddling, NDPS Act 1985, Information Technology Rules 2021, Telegram, Illicit Drug Abuse

I. INTRODUCTION

Amidst the contemporary digital landscape, characterized by pervasive connectivity and the omnipresence of social media platforms, a troubling trend has surfaced: the proliferation of illicit drug trade and consumption facilitated through online chat groups. This phenomenon embodies a complex interplay of technological advancements, social dynamics, and regulatory challenges, necessitating a thorough examination to unravel its intricacies and implications. This research embarks on a comprehensive investigation into the multifaceted issue, drawing upon a diverse array of scholarly literature spanning disciplines such as criminology, sociology, public health, and cyber forensics. With a focal point on the Telegram platform, the study aims to illuminate the mechanisms driving the promotion of illicit drug peddling and usage within virtual communities.

At the forefront of this inquiry lies the recognition of Telegram as a significant space for peer-led harm reduction communities and interventions (Rolando et al., 2023; Esther & Department of Publications and Extension, 2023; Rolando et al., 2023). These seminal works provide invaluable insights into the dynamics of online chat groups, emphasizing their potential for both harm reduction efforts and the dissemination of illicit substances. Building upon this foundation, the present research endeavors to delve deeper into the nuanced interactions and discourse patterns within these digital spaces. The proliferation of illicit drug trade and usage on social media platforms has raised pertinent questions regarding platform surveillance and resistance (Akbari & Gabdulhakov, 2019; Tsai et al., 2019). As individuals and groups navigate the digital landscape, they engage in a delicate dance of evasion and detection, presenting challenges for law enforcement agencies and platform administrators alike. By exploring the intricate interplay between surveillance mechanisms and user behaviors, this study aims to elucidate the dynamics of platform-mediated drug transactions.

Moreover, the research seeks to contextualize these findings within the broader organizational structures of drug markets (May & Hough, 2004; Demant et al., 2019). As traditional marketplaces evolve in response to digital advancements, understanding the underlying mechanisms of supply and demand becomes increasingly crucial. By examining the pathways through which illicit substances are sourced, distributed, and consumed within virtual communities, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the contemporary drug landscape.

Acknowledging the role of regulatory frameworks in shaping the digital domain (Patil & Pandey, 2022; Esther & Department of Publications and Extension, 2023), this research underscores the necessity for ongoing adaptation and innovation in policy development. Legislative measures such as the Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (NDPS) Act of 1985 and the Information Technology (IT) Rules of 2021 play a pivotal role in governing online behavior and curbing illicit activities. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the need for robust forensic examination techniques within the domain of cyber forensics (Watters & Phair, 2012; Rupa & Gangopadhyay, 2020). As illicit activities migrate to digital platforms, traditional investigative methods must evolve to keep pace with technological advancements. By leveraging cutting-edge forensic tools and methodologies, law enforcement agencies can enhance their capacity to detect and disrupt online drug trafficking networks.

In conclusion, this research represents a concerted effort to unravel the complexities of illicit drug activities in the digital age. By synthesizing insights from a diverse range of scholarly works, it aims to provide a nuanced understanding of the phenomenon and offer practical solutions for addressing its myriad challenges.

II. AIM OF THE RESEARCH

This research aims to understand how online chat groups, particularly on Telegram, facilitate illicit drug trade and consumption. By analyzing 100 public chat groups, the study seeks to uncover the dynamics of drug peddling and usage, highlight societal implications, and advocate for better regulation and enforcement measures.

III. METHODOLOGY

A thorough and comprehensive study was undertaken to examine how users interact with illicit drug peddling and consumption within the Telegram ecosystem, leveraging a sample size consisting of 100 public groups. This extensive analysis encompassed various dimensions, including the nature of shared content, communication dynamics among participants, methods employed for procurement and distribution of illicit substances, and the prevalence of discussions related to drug use. Moreover, the research aimed to identify notable trends such as the utilization of encryption methods and the adoption of specific jargon within these digital communities. Through meticulous scrutiny, the study sought to illuminate the mechanisms underlying illicit drug activities on Telegram, thereby elucidating the challenges faced by law enforcement and regulatory bodies in addressing such illicit practices in online environments.

1. Documenting the Default Settings of Telegram User Profiles: Documentation initially centred on recording the default settings of users' Telegram profiles, with particular emphasis on instances where the associated mobile number lacked prior association with a Telegram account. This documentation was deemed crucial due to its significant impact on the accessibility and user engagement dynamics within public groups and channels on the Telegram platform.

Default settings
Data and storage settings, Privacy and Security settings, Account inactivity settings

Table:1 The parameters of default settings

2. Evaluating the Accessibility of Public Telegram Groups: The methodology for assessing the accessibility of public Telegram groups and channels aimed to achieve a sample size of 100 through a systematic approach. This approach tackled the challenges associated with accessing these groups and channels. It involved utilizing various methods, including third-party websites, Telegram chat bots, the built-in Telegram search function (Fig. 1-3), and leveraging the default setting "Invites: Everybody." External websites served as repositories for public Telegram groups and channels, facilitating efficient discovery and ensuring sample diversity. Telegram chat bots were employed within the platform to help users locate groups and channels based on specific criteria, thus enabling targeted searches and aligning samples with research objectives. Additionally, the "Invites—Everybody" setting allowed unrestricted joining through invitation links, thereby broadening accessibility. This comprehensive methodology not only achieved a representative sample but also provided valuable insights for future research endeavors exploring user behavior within the Telegram ecosystem.

Figure: 1 shows the chat bot (Promotes public groups)

Figure: 2 shows the search option (Promotes public groups)

Figure: 3 shows third party websites (Promotes public groups)

Figure: 4 shows the sample size of chatting groups

3. Obtaining Chat History Extraction Methods in Public Telegram Groups: The acquisition of chat history extraction methods in public Telegram groups and channels involved a sample size of 100 Telegram groups and channels, specifically chatting groups ($n = 100$). This stratified sampling approach aimed to achieve a comprehensive understanding of user interaction within the Telegram ecosystem across diverse categories. To ensure the capture of all relevant information from the samples, three distinct methods of chat history extraction were employed.

3.1 Exporting data and chat history within the Telegram ecosystem: Chat history extraction within the Telegram ecosystem was executed through various methods, with the chosen approach contingent upon the specific data of interest concerning the chat history of the respective groups and channels. Extraction was solely feasible on a desktop platform, as this functionality remained unavailable on mobile devices, thereby necessitating the use of a desktop environment for extraction purposes.

3.1.1 Chat history acquisition: The primary method entailed targeted extraction of chat history data from the 100 sample groups, enabling comprehensive data acquisition. Each sample underwent a separate extraction, facilitating in-depth analysis. This method supported comparative studies on chat history characteristics across different group and channel types, considering factors such as primary function and overall functionality. For instance, it allowed for comparison between public news channels and private social interaction groups in terms of content and dynamics.

Procedure followed - Chat history acquisition:

Open the conversation you want to save → Tap the three vertical dots and select "Export chat history" → Choose the items you want to save - text messages → Check the boxes next to your chosen items and adjust the download limit if needed → Customize the format, download path, and date range → Click "Export" to save the chat history

3.1.2 Exporting entire chat history: This study employed two distinct extraction methodologies. One method utilized the export functionality inherent in the Telegram ecosystem, yielding outputs in both human-readable HTML and machine-readable JSON formats. The second method centered on a thorough examination of Telegram's legal and operational frameworks, as well as the functionality of its chat bots, user interfaces, and engagement mechanisms. Nevertheless, the former method encountered constraints in extracting complete chat histories from groups or channels. Moreover, to augment the research's breadth and depth, supplementary data sources such as case studies and court statements were integrated.

Procedure followed - Export telegram data: -

Tap the three horizontal lines at the top-left corner → Go to Settings > Advanced → Scroll down and select Export Telegram data → Choose the data type (like text messages), adjust the size limit, format, and download location → Tap Export to save your chat history.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study underscores the significant prevalence of illicit conversations related to drug trafficking and drug abuse within public chat groups on messaging platforms such as Telegram. The ease of access to these groups facilitates user participation, thereby increasing the risk of individuals either becoming victims of or perpetrators of drug-related offenses, driven by monetary incentives and peer influence. Previous research has documented the presence of illicit activities such as pornography, online prostitution, and sexual offenses against minors within public chat groups on platforms like Telegram. However, recent observations indicate a marked shift towards discussions centered on drug trafficking and drug abuse. These conversations often facilitate the direct sale and usage of illicit drugs and are sometimes linked to the arrangement of sexual acts or hookups in exchange for drugs.

In accordance with the Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (NDPS) Act 1985, the promotion, sale, or usage of any form of drugs is a criminal offense. Despite this, perpetrators exploit the relatively anonymous and less regulated environment of chat applications to engage in and promote these illegal activities. This underscores the urgent need for authorities to implement more stringent measures to monitor and prevent such offenses on social media platforms. The findings suggest that chat applications serve as covert venues for these illegal activities, complicating enforcement efforts. Therefore, there is a critical need for enhanced surveillance and intervention strategies by law enforcement and regulatory bodies to curb the use of social media platforms for drug trafficking and abuse. By addressing these challenges, authorities can better protect the public from the harms associated with illicit drug activities facilitated through online chat groups.

4.1 Relevance in terms of Forensic Investigation:

This study underscores the necessity for advanced investigative techniques in cyber forensics, especially concerning the evidentiary and integrity value of chat histories extracted from electronic devices, such as mobile phones, of individuals involved in drug-related offenses. Ensuring the proper updating of a database that includes each drug and its various names (including terms in native languages, code words, etc.) through continuous observation and interaction with these chat groups is essential.

For example, UFED (Universal Forensic Extraction Device) is a software tool used for extracting chat histories. The extracted data, typically presented in PDF format, requires meticulous verification by forensic professionals. Without a regularly updated database, these professionals may identify common drugs like marijuana but may struggle to recognize code words or native language terms used in conversations (Fig. 4-6). This limitation can result in the omission of crucial evidence.

The challenges are further compounded when forensic professionals conduct Inter-Laboratory Comparison (ILC) among forensic science laboratories (FSLs). Discrepancies in identifying drug-related terms due to outdated or incomplete databases can impact the consistency and accuracy of forensic analyses across different laboratories. Therefore, it is imperative to maintain an up-to-date, comprehensive database of drug nomenclature to ensure that forensic professionals can accurately interpret chat histories and identify illicit activities, regardless of the language or code words used.

Addressing these challenges will enhance the accuracy and reliability of cyber forensic investigations, ultimately improving the efficacy of law enforcement efforts in combating drug-related crimes on social media platforms.

Figure: 5 shows the prevalence of the word 'weed'

Figure: 6 shows the prevalence of the word 'ganja'

Figure: 7 shows the prevalence of the word 'marijuana'

V. CONCLUSION

This research underscores the significant prevalence of illicit drug trade and consumption within public chat groups on Telegram. The ease of access to these groups significantly increases the risk of individuals becoming involved in drug-related offenses, driven by monetary incentives and peer influence. The study reveals a recent shift in online illicit activities, expanding from previously documented issues such as pornography, online prostitution, and sexual offenses against minors, towards drug trafficking and abuse. Despite the stringent provisions of the Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances (NDPS) Act, perpetrators exploit the anonymity and lack of regulation in chat applications to conduct illegal activities. This creates substantial challenges for enforcement, emphasizing the urgent need for enhanced surveillance and intervention strategies by law enforcement and regulatory bodies.

Advanced cyber forensic techniques are crucial, especially regarding the evidentiary and integrity value of chat histories extracted from electronic devices. A comprehensive and continuously updated database that includes each drug and its various names, including native language terms and code words, is essential for accurate evidence extraction and interpretation. Tools such as the Universal Forensic Extraction Device (UFED) are employed for this purpose; however, forensic professionals must meticulously verify the extracted data to avoid omitting crucial evidence. The need for consistency and accuracy in identifying drug-related terms is further underscored by Inter-Laboratory Comparisons (ILCs) among forensic science laboratories.

The study recommends updating regulatory frameworks, such as the NDPS Act 1985 and Information Technology Rules 2021, to address evolving challenges posed by digital platforms. Additionally, public awareness campaigns are vital to educate individuals about the dangers of illicit drug use and the legal consequences of participation. Future research should explore the application of artificial intelligence and machine learning to detect and analyze illicit drug-related conversations on social media platforms. Integrating insights from criminology, sociology, public health, and cyber forensics will provide a more holistic understanding and inform more effective intervention strategies. This research offers actionable insights aimed at informing policy development, law enforcement strategies, and platform governance practices. By addressing the complexities of illicit drug activities in the digital age, it seeks to mitigate their impact on virtual communities and safeguard public health and safety.

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